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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS SERUM ENZYME LEVELS IN
SEVERAL LIVER DISEASES**Dr Shahroz Zafar Bhatti¹, Dr. Aqssa Munir², Dr. Fajar Ikram³¹ Rawal institute of health science, Islamabad² Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore³ Gujranwala Medical College, Gujranwala**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Patients with chronic liver diseases are asymptomatic or have only vague non-specific symptoms. Effective medical treatments for chronic liver disease (before cirrhosis is established) are becoming increasingly available and since abnormal LFTs may be the only indication of these diseases.

Aims: Enzymes study of various liver diseases.

Place and Duration: In the General Medicine department for six months from October 2019 to March 2020 in Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Methods: serum Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Gamma Glutamyl transferase (Gamma GT), Alanine and Aspartate amino transferases were estimated in viral Hepatitis, Alcoholic liver diseases, Obstructive jaundice, cirrhosis of the liver. It was observed that obstructive jaundice shows higher levels of ALP levels followed by alcoholic liver disease, viral hepatitis, cirrhosis of the liver. Viral hepatitis shows higher rise of SGOT, SGPT levels, followed by alcoholic liver disease, obstructive jaundice, and cirrhosis of the liver. Gamma Glutamyl transferase enzymes highest levels are seen in alcoholic liver disease. **Conclusion:** These enzymatic variations are useful to diagnose the disease and classify them according to etiology.

Keywords: Transfer gamma glutamyl, Cirrhosis of the Liver, Alcoholic Liver Disease.

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INTRODUCTION:

Liver disease is a general term for any damage that reduces liver function. As a large organ, the liver shares with many other skills to perform functions with a huge reserve ability. Chronic alcoholism, pancreatic disease, myocardial infarction, renal failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and increased levels of gamma glutamyl transferase (GGT) in diabetes¹⁻². In liver disease, the height of GGT is parallel to serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and is very sensitive to diseases of the bile ducts³⁻⁴. GGT levels in alcoholic liver disease are more or less parallel to alcohol consumption. GGT is an important enzyme for the detection of alcoholic liver disease. In patients with obstructive jaundice, very high levels of ALP are observed, as well as in the serum of bones, kidneys, leukocytes, placental and intestinal diseases. Obstructive jaundice increases due to ALP cancer, common ductal stone, cholecystitis or bile duct structure. ALP is an important enzyme in the diagnosis of obstructive jaundice. However, the primary hepatoma can see a significant increase in AST. Serum ALT levels are increased in chronic liver diseases such as cirrhosis, hepatitis and non-alcoholic hepatitis SEATO (NASH)⁵⁻⁶. For this reason, it has been reported that four enzymes: GGT, ALP, SGOT, SGPT are useful parameters in the diagnosis of various liver diseases⁷⁻⁸. However, in a recent review, some of these enzymes are not listed for use in the diagnosis of various liver diseases. In these cases, the purpose of these studies is to study these enzymes in various liver diseases and to assess the diagnostic significance⁹⁻¹⁰.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A total of 80 individual liver patients who applied to the Hospital's General Medicine department for six months from October 2019 to March 2020 in Jinnah Hospital, Lahore were included in this study, with the approval of the Corporate Ethics Board and the consent of each patient. All are aged 35-50 of both sexes.

Patient grouping: Group1: Check for healthy volunteers (N-20).

Group 2: Cirrhosis (N-20),

Group3: Alcoholic liver disease 20,

Group 4: Diagnosis of obstructive jaundice.

Group 5: viral hepatitis. Standard examination of data on personal history, onset of the disease, alcohol consumption and treatment of liver diseases. 10 ml of venous blood samples were taken in tubes, separated by serum centrifuges and used to predict SGOT, SGPT, ALP & Gamma GT4 serum. The International Federation of Clinical Chemistry predicts that the kinetic method (IFCC) is the SGPT serum, SGPT is in a state of high

concentration and is present at lower concentrations in the liver and kidneys, heart, skeletal muscles, pancreas and lungs. Increased levels can often be seen as a result of primary liver disease, such as cirrhosis, cancer, viral or toxic hepatitis, reducing levels in patients with kidney dialysis and vitamin B6 deficiency.

L-alanine+2-oxoglutarate-- ALT Pyruvate + L-Glutamate, pyruvate + NADH-- -LDH L-Lactate + NAD (ALT=Alanine aminotransferase, LDH=Lactate dehydrogenase) values expressed in IU/L, Normal values; Females:0-31IU/L, in males:0-40IU/L, at 37°C,(5- 7).SERUM SGOT was estimated by IFCC Method, Kinetic without Pyridoxal Phosphate, SGOT occurs in all human tissues and is present in large amount in liver, renal, cardiac, and skeletal muscle tissue. Increased levels are associated with liver disease or damage myocardial infarction, muscular dystrophy and cholecystitis. Decreased levels are observed in undergoing renal dialysis and those with B6 deficiency. values are expressed in IU/L. Principle: L-spartate+2xoglutarate SGOT oxaloacetate +L-Glutamate, oxaloacetate+ NADH MDH Malate +NAD+ sample pyruvate +NADH L-Lactate + NAD, (AST=Aspartate aminotransferase, LDH=Lactate dehydrogenase, MDH=Malate dehydrogenase) Normal values; Women: up to 31IU/L, Men:upto37IU/L(8-10). SERU ALP is found in practically all tissues of the body but in higher concentrations in the osteoblasts of bone, liver placenta, kidney, and lactating mammary glands. Increase ALP is seen in osteomalacia and rickets, low levels of ALP may be observed in conditions which causes arrested bone growth or in hypophosphatasia. SERUM ALP was estimated by P-Nitro phenyl phosphate method. AMP+4-NPP+H₂O----ALP 4-nitrophenol+phosphate, and values expressed in IU/L Normal values; Females:50-170 IU/L. Male:50-96IU/L10-14. SERUM GGT elevation parallels that of ALP and is sensitive of biliary track disease. GGT is the key enzyme for diagnosis of alcoholic liver disease. SERUM GAMMA GT was estimated by kinetic method, principle: Gluta- C+ Glycylglycine L-Gamma -Glutamyl- Glycylglycine+5-Amino-2-nitrobenzoicacid, GLUPA-C:L-Gamma-glutamyl-3-carboxy-p- nitroanilide, and values expressed in U/L Normal values;Females:5-32U/L,Males:10-45u/L.

RESULTS:

The biochemical results of this study are expressed as the following results, and the results are expressed as mean and SD, normal values are used to compare values, averages for all study parameters and calculated for patients with SD and control. The p-0.001 value is relatively important.

DISCUSSION:

PARAMETER	CIRRHOSIS OF LIVER	ALCOHOLIC LIVER DISEASE	VIRAL HEPATITIS	OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE
SGOT(IU/L)	95.0±9.7	239.2±15.4	290.0±17.05	91.9±9.5
SGPT (IU/L)	98.5±9.9	152.0±12.3	499.3±22.3	96.35±9.81
ALP (IU/L)	151.2±12.3	222.15±17.45	183.85±13.6	678.45±26.04
GGT(IU/L)	90.3± 9.2	480.0±21.9	70.5±6.8	180.6±12.5

In this study, serum ALP and GGT levels were higher in all cases of alcoholic liver disease. However, the second alcoholic liver disease increased on average to about 6 times the average of their average normal value, which was much higher than GGT in all cases¹¹⁻¹². It is known that GGT and ALP in serum are high in all cases of alcoholic liver disease, and the importance of these enzymes is the primary enzymes of alcoholic liver disease¹³⁻¹⁴. In addition, these enzymes increase in other liver diseases, such as obstructive jaundice; Due to this increase above normal values, alcoholic liver disease was observed. Alcohol seemed like a better parameter for an old diagnosis that compares the importance of GGT and ALP in liver disease. Serum SGPT and SGOT increased their normal value in viral hepatitis 6 times, while ALP levels only tripled normal value. The increase in SGPT in SGPT shows a greater increase than SGOT, a better indicator of viral hepatitis than the old one. A slight increase in the concentration of both enzymes in serum was observed only in most other cases of liver disease with a significant increase in viral hepatitis¹⁵. The concentration of ALP in serum increased to 8 times the normal value in obstructive jaundice, an important enzyme in the obstructive diagnosis of jaundice. Predicting these parameters is a guide to assessing the severity of liver damage and is also a good predictive measure of values. Regardless of liver etiology, estimating these parameters provides a complete picture of liver disease significantly.

CONCLUSION:

Taken together, it shows that GGT levels (kinetic method) are more useful than ALP for the diagnosis of alcoholic liver disease. On the other hand, SGPT (IFCC method, Kinetic) is definitely a better indicator of viral hepatitis than SGOT (IFCC method, Kinetic without pyridoxal phosphate). ALP (P-nitrophen phosphate) is a specific diagnostic parameter that indicates obstructive jaundice. This paper supports their inclusion and application as reliable tests for the diagnosis of specific liver diseases. As the study is conducted in a rural community, in and around Kadapa, most patients suffer from jaundice in the later stages. It was believed that the season of the year was due to illiteracy, superstition, and ignorance of these varieties of the disease. For this reason, it is very important to make rural society aware of the importance of alcohol, drug abuse, malnutrition, hepatitis and childhood immunization.

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